

THE ROLE OF MARKETING IN THE COMPANY "UZBEKNEFTEGAZ" JSC

¹Musayeva Shoirazimovna, ²Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna

¹Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service

²Associate professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service

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Abstract. This article discusses the promotion of products and services in the market, various messages, including advertising, PR activities, digital marketing and social media, to attract new customers, and pays attention to developing customer loyalty, quality service, timely support and solving customer problems.

Keywords: marketing, petroleum products, advertising, sales, customers, service, market, trend, services.

INTRODUCTION. The role of marketing in the company "Uzbekneftegaz" JSC is an important and integral implementation of its successful activities. Marketing at "Uzbekneftegaz" JSC plays a key role in achieving high performance goals, strengthening market positions, realizing sales and meeting customer needs.

One of the main tasks of marketing in "Uzbekneftegaz" is the market and understanding of customers. The company actively analyzes the oil and gas product market, customers, trends and changes in the industry in order to sell its products and services on demand. engages in marketing research, determines the target audience, segments the market and deals with the distribution strategy of its products and services.

Product positioning and brand building are also important marketing tasks at Uzbekneftegaz. The company includes creating unique and attractive offerings for its customers, seeking advantages and competitive advantages, and establishing its brand as a reliable and quality supplier of oil and gas products. Marketing roles and promotions play an important role in valuing a company and attracting customers.

Marketing also showed the results of calculating the pricing policy of Uzbekneftegaz. By analyzing market conditions, competitive prices and demand, the marketing department determines the best prices for the company's products. This includes not only defining base prices, but also developing different types of pricing such as seasonal discounts, bonuses and special offers for customers.

The marketing department of "Uzbekneftegaz" JSC is also responsible for promoting products and services on the market. It registers and highlights campaigns, includes a variety of messages including advertising, PR activities, digital marketing and social media to attract new customers and on a regular basis. Marketing also pays attention to developing customer loyalty, quality service, timely support and solving customer problems.

Ultimately, marketing plays an important role in Uzbekneftegaz JSC, helping to build a successful and developmentally important development, to compete with the market and the need for customer needs. The effective use of promotional strategies and tools allows the company to strengthen its guard and limit growth in the oil and gas industry. Marketing at "Uzbekneftegaz" JSC plays a key role in achieving high performance goals, strengthening market positions, realizing sales and meeting customer needs.

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Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. Product positioning and brand building are also important marketing tasks at Uzbekneftegaz. The company includes creating unique and attractive offerings for its customers, seeking advantages and competitive advantages, and establishing its brand as a reliable and quality supplier of oil and gas products. Marketing roles and promotions play an important role in valuing a company and attracting customers.

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Ultimately, marketing plays an important role in Uzbekneftegaz JSC, helping to build a successful and developmentally important development, to compete with the market and the need for customer needs. In order to determine the potential of the company, I identified the strengths and weaknesses with the help of a SWOT analysis.

Table 1

SWOT analysis of Uzbekneftegaz JSC

<p style="text-align: center;">Strengths:</p> <p>1. Vast oil and gas reserves 2. Vertical integration the company identifying various sectors of the oil and gas industry includes exploration and production, transportation, refining and marketing, which allows you to control the entire production cycle and its activities</p> <p>3. Geographic location</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Weak sides:</p> <p>1. Lack of technological development 2. Limited diversification 3. Limited access to a new market</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Functions:</p> <p>Development of alternative energy sources "Uzbekneftegaz" JSC can consume and consume alternative energy sources such as solar and wind energy in order to expand its</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Danger:</p> <p>1. Falling oil and gas prices 2. Regulatory restrictions 3. Competition for availability: other international oil and gas companies can</p>

portfolio and consume to changes in the world energy. 2. International cooperation 3. Improved performance	provide competition for access to resources, new projects and children.
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“Uzbekneftegaz” uses the development of minerals, using both developed oil and gas reserves, vertical integration and geographical location. These factors allow the company to provide a stable source of income and control the entire cycle.

Opportunities for Uzbekneftegaz include the development of alternative energy sources such as solar and wind power to diversify its portfolio and penetrate the changing energy industry. Also, the company can expand its worldwide cooperation and increase the infrastructure in the field of consumption, which will expand the sales market and greater delivery of energy carriers.

The effective use of advocacy strategies and tools allows the company to strengthen its guard and limit growth in the oil and gas industry. Marketing in JSC "Uzbekneftegaz" JSC also plays an important role in the field of internal marketing and communications. Internal marketing is aimed at creating a positive corporate culture, motivating employees and strengthening their commitment to the company and its goals. The company "Uzbekneftegaz" JSC has identified a high degree of involvement and motivation of its employees, realizing that satisfied and motivated employees have contributed to the success of the company. The marketing department of the volume of communication programs, the implementation of corporate events and events, the support of team spirit, the exchange of proposals and the provision of information between departments of companies.

In addition, marketing at "Uzbekneftegaz" JSC plays the role of supporting sustainable development and social responsibility. Jointly includes compliance with high requirements in the field of ecology, safety and social sphere. The marketing department actively communicates these values and initiatives of the companies, freely distributes and trusts both representatives and external parties, such as customers, partners and the society at large.

Moreover, marketing at "Uzbekneftegaz" JSC plays a role in the introduction of new technologies and innovations in the oil and gas industry. Joint use of advanced industry, introduction and implementation of new methods of production, transfer and use of oil and gas resources. The marketing department conducts market research and analyzes industry research to identify new opportunities for growth and development of the company. In addition, he also receives information about new products and technologies, adapting them to market and customer requirements.

In general, marketing plays an important and multifaceted role in Uzbekneftegaz JSC. It explores not only aspects such as market, product promotion, and customer acquisition, but also the scope of aspects such as strengthening corporate culture, employee engagement, and broad development. Marketing is essential to achieving a company's important goals and requires its effectiveness in the oil and gas market. Due to his role in the JSC "Uzbekneftegaz", marketing a wide range of interests and interests in front of competitors. Consider some of the main aspects of marketing in a company:

1. Market analysis and research: The marketing department of Uzbekneftegaz JSC conducts market research, evaluates consumer behavior, analyzes estimates and determines industry trends. It helps to predict customer needs and preferences, predict market changes and play strategic marketing.

2. **Products and Services:** The marketing department at Uzbekneftegaz JSC plays a key role in the development of new products and services. It analyzes market needs and researches, researches and consults with other departments of companies to determine which products and services should be improved or improved. The marketing department also defines the features of the products and establishes their useful features for customers to keep and keep.

3. **Promotion of products:** The marketing department of the company "Uzbekneftegaz" JSC is acutely aware of the risks of increasing products on the market. This includes advertising campaigns, public relations activities, participation in exhibitions and conferences, creation of promotional materials and use of various discussions to attract the attention of customers and draw attention to the company's products.

4. **Brand management:** Marketing helps Uzbekneftegaz JSC build and manage its brand. Marketing specialists work on creating a unique image of the company, creating its advertising and advantages over competitors. This includes developing a logo, corporate identity, effectively communicating brands with engagement and messaging, and respecting and honoring the brand in all marketing materials and communications.

5. **Feedback and customer satisfaction:** The marketing department of "Uzbekneftegaz" JSC actively collects customer satisfaction and analyzes their satisfaction with the company's products and services. This contributes to the development of the place and area for improvement, as well as setting up more active service and customer sustainability.

6. **Innovation and development:** The marketing department of the company "Uzbekneftegaz" JSC follows modern technologies, trends and innovations in the oil and gas industry. It concludes the market and analyzes potential opportunities for the use of new products, services and processes. Marketing plays an important role in the commercialization and successful implementation of innovations, as well as in the high performance of the company in the market.

Marketing at Uzbekneftegaz JSC is an important factor in its success and growth. It helps a company build and strengthen its market position, attract and retain customers, develop and promote new products and services, and seek effective communication and collaboration both inside and outside the company. The marketing department plays an important role in the strategy of the company's strategy and its successful implementation, contributing to the sustainable development and performance of Uzbekneftegaz.

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